

Corrigendum: Comparison of spallation reaction models based on multiple-criteria decision analysis.

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In our recently published work, some errors that can impair your complete understanding were not noticed in the text. Corrections are as follows:

References (pag. 233):

Missed two references concerning the “IAEA Benchmark of Spallation Models” and the Table 1 Most common modern, transport codes. p. 230 right column. Two references should be added:

- IAEA Benchmark of Spallation Models, available at <https://www-nds.iaea.org/spallations/> [Accessed Feb 05 2018]
- David J-C (2015) Spallation reactions: A successful interplay between modeling and applications. The European Physical Journal A, 51:68. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epja/i2015-15068-1>

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References

- IAEA Benchmark of Spallation Models, available at <https://www-nds.iaea.org/spallations/> [Accessed Feb 05 2018]
- David J-C (2015) Spallation reactions: A successful interplay between modeling and applications. The European Physical Journal A, 51:68. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epja/i2015-15068-1>